

TRADITIONAL INSTITUTIONS AND UNDERDEVELOPMENT OF SOME RURAL COMMUNITIES IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA.

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ABSTRACT:

The traditional institution provides the basic ingredients for leadership structure in most African societies, especially in the rural areas of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It plays the critical role of controlling the collective fate of its subjects through the manipulation of traditional settings under the guise of acting on behalf of the people. This qualitative, multi-community study examines the contending narratives on the roles of traditional rulers in the perpetuation of slavery conditions and tendencies in rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. The study findings show that, marginalization, selfish interest, black politics, intimidation, and manipulation of youth groups are the tools employed by some traditional rulers to impede development while promoting poverty and enslavement among their subjects. The paper strongly recommends re-structuring of the traditional rulership system to stamp out the painful memories of slavery in African society.

Key words: Poverty, Slavery, Underdevelopment, Traditional Rulership and Democratic Doctrine.

Introduction

One of the greatest challenges of underdevelopment in Nigeria lies within the rural grassroot settings in our society. This natural human habitation is often left yearning for economic, social, cultural and political attentions. As a matter of fact, poverty and other economic crisis have become well entrenched in the rural areas of Nigeria. This unwholesome fact of life manifests in various forms ranging from, poor sanitation, disease, hunger among other social problems. This sordid situation may still be ignored or scoffed at, but they cannot be denied (Musa, 2010).

Due to the lack of a well articulated programme for rural development, there has been much variation in the administration and performance of rural development programme in Nigeria (Kamar, Lawal, Babangida, and Janun, 2014; Usoro and Peters, 2019). Musa (2010), observed that the concern for these problems has acquired a certain standing, a measure of discussing ability in the media and in some socio-economic, political, academic and religious institutions.

In Nigeria, rural development has not been centrally guided; instead of institutionalising a rural development ministry, the federal government has rationed the development programmes on several ministries and departments at both federal and state levels (Kamar *et al.* 2014). The crucial role of local government system as a link between government and the rural people remains unrealizable and these lapses according to Okeh (2010), have prompted a continued search for a new strategy for rural development in

Nigeria. The situation is that, traditional rulership as an institution in Nigeria seems to be placed within the gap for realisation of the rural development quest.

Traditional rulership as an institution was known in pre-colonial and early post-colonial eras of Nigeria as an institution of defence, morals establishment, development actualization, administrative body and bridge of good governance between the rural community dwellers and governments at the three tiers of leadership. The traditional rulership in the early era of Nigeria community which was the custodian of tradition, and culture created a dependable governance space characterized by mutual relationship between the followers and the leaders (Iproject, 2018). According to Ayuk, Owan, and Uyang, (2013), there were various traditional channels through which societies controlled crime. This includes the elders councils, chiefs, village heads etc; whose functions was the interpretation of the code of conduct and behaviour of the subsisting community as passed down from generations to generation. It is a fact that traditional societies did not have documented or written down laws to guide human conducts as observed in western societies, but it had a well established institutions for controlling crime and maintaining social order (Ayuk *et al.*, 2013).

Traditional leaders played the role of upholding the culture, tradition, norms and values in their domains. They are expected to co-operate with different levels of governments and its agencies to identify the needs of their communities and offer useful inputs in the processes involved in service delivery at the grassroot. They also played a role in disaster management and the promotion of indigenous knowledge system (The Pointer, 2018).

By the turn of the 21st century, the newly emerged class of politicians saw the traditional institutions as a threat to their grip on power and therefore, crippled the powers of the traditional institutions (Abubakar, 2015). The clamped down on the political power, neglect suffered by the traditional institutions in political decision making at the three levels of government, and the amassing of wealth within the politicians contributed to the resentment character- deficiency observed among some of the traditional rulers at the rural settings today (Peters and Basse, 2019).

According to Omole (2016), in Nigeria, one of the reasons for our inability to achieve sustainable democracy and development is the failure to harness the traditional political institutions. Traditional institution in Akwa Ibom State is administered through the State's Council of Chiefs under Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Local Government and Chieftaincy Affairs. Each local government has its council of chiefs headed by a paramount ruler who represents the local government traditional rulers council at the state level. Each community/village within a Local Government Area is governed by a village head who holds the traditional leadership of such community.

CONCEPTUAL ISSUES.

The following key concepts will be defined in this study. They are marginalization, black politic, Poverty, Slavery, Underdevelopment and Democratic Doctrine.

Marginalization: this concept refers to the process whereby something or someone is pushed to the edge of a group and accorded lesser importance. This is predominantly a social phenomenon by which a minority or sub-group is excluded, and their needs or desires ignored (Business Dictionary (2018)). Social Marginalization or exclusion is the process in which individuals or people are systematically blocked from (or denied full access to) various

rights, opportunities and resources that are normally available to members of a different group, and which are fundamental to social integration and observance of human rights within that particular group (e.g., housing, employment, healthcare, civic engagement, democratic participation, and due process) (IPSSJ, 2018).

Black Politics: this concept according to this study refers to the involvement of the community members in community activities toward the gains of the traditional leaderships only without the community members being aware of the reasons behind involvement in such activities.

Poverty: poverty refers to the state of one who lacks a usual or socially acceptable amount of money or material possessions. Poverty is said to exist when people lack the means to satisfy their basic needs (Britanica Encyclopaedia, 2018).

Slavery: slavery is any system in which principles of property law are applied to people, allowing individuals to own, buy and sell other individuals, as a de jure form of property (Brace, 2004). Within the context of this study any tendency or activity by individual or group of people that undermines the development, growth, and tends to perpetuate poverty and other adverse condition of life is conceptualised as slavery.

Underdevelopment: the term underdevelopment refers to that state of an economy where levels of living of masses are extremely low due to very low levels of per capita income resulting from low levels of productivity and high growth rates of population (Gupta, 2018).

Democratic Doctrine: this concept according to this study refer to the principles of democracy which sees government as a supreme power vested in the people and exercised directly by the people or by their elected agents through a free electoral system.

METHODS

Study Site

In Ikot Annang Village, Inua Eket Ikot Village, and Akpansung Village in Onna, Ibeno and Esit Eket Local Government Area, respectively, the people are basically farmers, hunters, and traders. The major cash crop found in the study areas is cassava. The religion of the people of the study areas is majorly Christianity. The areas are located within Eket Senatorial District in Akwa Ibom State. The population of each of the Local Government Area selected for the study as at 2016 was 89,000 for Esit Eket, 105,000 for Ibeno and 173,100 for Onna Local Government Areas. The study areas within the selected Local Government Areas have heads of the traditional institutions as village heads, who are the heads of communal affairs in their respective community.

Study design

Various qualitative techniques were used in the study (participant observation, key informant, life history and informal conversation) as prescribed by ethnographic principles (Peters, 2019). These generated data that were used in preparing a question guide for focus group discussions and In-depth interview guides. The interview guides were unstructured with open-ended questions. This was deliberately designed to give the participants the liberty to air their views exhaustively on issues raised. The participants gave their consent before being involved in the study. During interviews and focus group discussions participants were given light refreshments and some financial assistants as honorarium. Four FGD sessions were held, each session involved 8 discussants. The females had their sessions separate from males. Each FGD session lasted for 3 to 4 hours.

Participants and data collection

Participants of the study were mature adults between the age 30 years and above. Village heads and council members were purposely selected for the study. While other participants were randomly selected. The participants were randomly selected from three purposely selected communities from the three (3) local government areas: Ibeno, Esit Eket

and Onna Local Government Areas. A total of 285 participants were engaged in the study ($n= 285$). Community selection was based on similarities in the traditional leadership style of the village heads. All interviews with the study participants were in Ibibio language and were later translated into English language. Interviews and participant observations were first carried out in InuaEyet Ikot Village in Ibeno Local Government Area, followed by Akpanusung Village in Esit Eket Local Government Area and finally at Ikot Annang village in Onna Local Government Area.

Questions in the interview schedule were prepared to find out how the members of the communities are marginalized by their village heads, how they are compelled to involve in activities that benefits their community leaderships without their knowledge and how youth groups are manipulated toward the selfish interest of the village heads. Through participant observation, responses were sought inline with the daily experiences of the study participants in an holistic systematic approach.

Analyses

Dependency theory was used for the study. According to Dinko (2017) the theory argues that the real cause of underdevelopment of developing countries is the historical unequal relationship with the developed countries specifically colonialism. This school of development thinking according to Dinko (2017) was spearheaded by Andre Gunder Frank in his *Development of Underdevelopment* (1972). Analysis of data sought to explain key themes and variables in recorded interviews and participant observations conducted during the period of data collection. Qualitative analysis was used to analyse narratives. Thematic framework was generated and used by the researchers to code all qualitative datasets and participation observation field notes (Phillips, Ononokpono and Udofia, 2016). Microsoft Office 2010 was used by the researcher to analysed quantitative variables which were generated during interviews and participant observation, and simple descriptive analysis involving frequency and cross-tabulation techniques were used by the authors. Bar chart was used to show the analysis of number of respondents per theme or variable of the study.

RESULTS

Findings

The results of the study was based on data generated from in-depth interviews and participant observation from 285 study participants drawn from 3 communities in 3 local government areas in Akwa Ibom State. 95 (33.33%) participants were randomly selected from each of the 3 of the communities from Ibeno, Esit Eket and Onnalocal government areas.

Demographic characteristics of the study participants show that 118 (41.4%) were males and 167 (58.6%) were females. Among the participants, 19 (6.7%) were civil servants, 120 (42.1%) were self-employed, while 146 (51.2%) were unemployed. 109 (38.2%) were aged between 30 and 39 years, 86 (30.2%) were aged between 40 and 49 years, 73 (25.6%) were aged between 50 and 59 years and 17 (6.0%) were aged between 60 years and above. 63 (22.1%) were single, 87 (30.5%) were married, 28 (9.8%) were divorced, 56 (19.7%) were widowed, 27 (9.5%) were co-habitated and 24 (8.4%) were seperated. 97 (34%) had no formal education, 136 (41.7%) were holders of First School Leaving Certificate (FLSC), 22 (7.7%) were holders of NCE, 25 (8.8%) were holders of OND, while 5 (1.8%) were holders of Degree.

Corbin and Strauss (2008) cited in Ogula (2015) noted that respondents use language in interviews inways that conceptualize actions, meaning and direction for the researcher. In

theme development process, respondents' expressions are quoted verbatim, and ellipses points used to indicate where material has been removed to contract the quote; researcher emphases are indicated in italics (Ogula, 2015).

Marginalization

It was observed that not every major family (Ekpuk) that make up the village has always been in support of their village leadership and vice versa. This created situations whereby some parts of the community suffered marginalization during certain leadership tenure in the community. In answering questions on marginalization, majority of the study participants ($n = 221/77.5\%$) in their responses to interview ascertained that they have suffered marginalization by their present community leadership. From recorded interview, most of the study participants from the 3 communities (Ikot Annang, InuaEyet Ikot and Akpanusung in Onna, Ibeno and Esit Eket Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria) narrated that they are not part of anything or any beneficial activity from their community leadership since the enthronement of their present village heads. One of the respondents from Ikot Annang community in Onna Local Government Area narrates:

We have not been carried along by the community leadership for a very long time now. We don't even know anything that is going on in the village apart from such things that they need or demand from us. The village head does not involve my husband's family in his administration. Everything that comes into the community as compensation, donations or help from government or any corporation, the village leadership will not notify us until the programme is over and when my husband confront them for reasons of such omission, they will give one excuse or the other.

Most of the respondents reported that major families (Ekpuk) who refuse to show loyalty and total support to the village leadership have always lost their place of favour in the leadership structure of their community. Responses show that marginalization of some parts or members of the community resulted from disloyalty from the subjects toward the village/community leadership. A respondent from InuaEyet Ikot in his report stated that;

If you refuse to support the decision of the village head, you will be seen and counted as disobedient or disloyal to the village leadership. Therefore, you will be neglected in all the activities that goes on except such things like contributions, levies and other demands from the community members.

Another respondent from Ikot Annang community in Onna Local Government Area, a woman narrated that:

The village leadership has been highly selfish and selective. He only want to favour his family members in everything while others are dying in poverty. For instance, Government came in for compensations, the village head did not called the community together to inform them on the state of things. We heard it from the neighbouring community and before we got to his place, the people have already pass through our farm lands to another community. Can this bring development to the land? Can this transform our lives in this village? Can this make us happy with him? No, there will be problem if he is paid and we do not collect such comensation too.

From data collected on this theme “marginalization” from interviews and observations, factors like disloyalty, disobedient and internal criticism formed basis for marginalization, which some families and community members are neglected by their community leaders. Neglect or abandonment of some parts or members of the community by community leaders has brought about poverty, underdevelopment and positioned these neglected members of the community as slaves in their own communities. Findings show that they are often forced to comply with the demands and order of the community leadership since they mostly formed the minority and the opposition group within their communities.

When any member or family in the community does not support or show loyalty to the leadership of the community, there is bound to be internal criticism from which actions that are contrary to the traditions of the community are set into the community affairs through the parties concern. This finding ascertain the position of Adelugba, Ujomu, and Amanor-Boadu (2007), that internal criticism can lead to abandonment of a tradition.

Black Politics

Facts from observations and reported narratives remain that there exist a high level of partisan politics practiced by community leaderships in most of the rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. Biased politics in the traditional institution is very high in some of the villages in Akwa Ibom State. Majority of the respondents ($n = 179/62.8\%$) in their responses to questions about politics in the traditional institution of their communities reported that; politics has eaten deep into traditional institutions against what was known as pure, morally right and inherited leadership structure of the traditional positions, coronated through sacred rite of passage. One of the respondents from Akpansung Village in Esit Eket Local Government Area in his response narrated that:

We haven't seen things as we have seen this days in our community as compare to the days of my father. There was nothing like lobbying for the village head throne or lobbying for positions in the village leadership of our community. Headship in my father's day was an inheritance of the royal family otherwise known as Akpan family (Akpan-Akpansung). Today, there is nothing like royal family because of claims and lobbying for headship and other positions in the village leadership. This has always kept the village backward because of delays and crises, making the village to suffer unnecessarily.

Prejudiced displayed in traditional institutions' politics according to most of the study participants, have contributed to underdevelopment of most rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. This is so because, according to narrative from respondents politics begin right from the process of finding a successor when the leadership stool is vacant. The process of coming to a consensus person do witnessed a lot of politicking which often create division among the people and most times the people themselves are manipulated to participate in support of views of an individual without having clearer understanding of what exactly they are contracting. One of the respondents from Ikot Annang in Onna Local Government Area in her response reported that;

Village headships is no longer an issue of traditional inheritance, some people who feel that they can lobby and have the people intimidated will rise may be because they have one support or the other from one big politician and enforce himself on the people through diverse means of politics. So

those who want to stand for the right thing will be considered as rebels and threatened as such. But the problem is always that the community will suffer from so many things because there are things he (the village head) may not be able to do alone, because such things need the presence and traditional rites from the opposition elders and sometimes there may be things that suppose to benefits everbody, he (the village head) will want to take it for himself and his family.

Another study participant from Akpansung Community in Esit Eket Local Government Area in his responses reported that;

Politics is everything in Akwa Ibom State, if you do not know politics you cannot survive even in a rural community like this. It is politics that make our village leaders to tell us to go out and answer questions when government came to see how to compensate us on our farm lands which they want to take for projects. They selected people who can give the kind of answers they want to give to those people and left us who are the real land owners and users. One person even called his wife who never farm, who is a teacher to come and be part of the people who will receive compensation as farmers. This is black politics and this community have been suffering from this for a long time now.

Information gathered through interview shows that most of the respondents agree to the existence of partisan politics within the traditional institutions against an institution that was void of politics in the early Nigerian traditional society. Extracted naratives point to the effects of these politics as leading the community into abandonment of traditions and morals which have contributed to devesre socio-cultural and economic challenges experienced within the contemporary rural traditional society. This finding ascertainthe thatthe bane of the traditional institution in the previous periods had been their actual or suspected involvement in partisan politics. In contemporary Nigeria, the institution has no business in partisan politics (Achebe, 2017).

Youth Groups' Manipulation

Youth participation refers to the involvement of youths in responsible, challenging action that meets genuine needs, with opportunities for planning and/or decision-making affecting others in an activity whose impact or consequence is extended to others i.e., outside or beyond the youth participants themselves (Cornwal, 2010). Against this explanation have been the use of youths in most rural communities in Akwa Ibom State as stated by majority of the respondents. Most of the respondents ($n = 212/74.4\%$) were of the opinion that most of their youths have been misled by their community leaders in various cases to project and defend the interest of the community leaders instead of the general citizens. It was gathered that youth groups have been machineries used by some of the community leaders to fulfilled their selfish interest and desire through unethical and un-traditonal use of community youth groups. One of the respondents from InuaEyet Ikot in Ibeno Local Government Area in her responses to questions narrated that;

Youths in our community have been used by the community leadership to intimidte people anyhow on issue and cases that suppose to be rightly deliberated upon or decided by the people. If the majority of the people refuse to agree on some issues, before you know it the youths in a group will come to warn you and your family and threaten you. Since you

cannot withstand these youths and you want your family to be safe, you can only withdraw from everything that should give you problem with these youths through the village leadership. We have been living as slaves in our own land.

The participation of youth groups in community activities has been shifted from positive community impact activities to diverse kind of ill and destructive activities that impede community development and progress. Gathered information show that majority of the respondents reported in their narratives that contemporary rural community youth associations or groups are majorly instruments in the hands of community leaders and some politicians who use the youths to control the rural populace toward achieving their selfish interest despite the yearning and traditions of the people. One of the respondents from Akpansung Community in Esit Eket Local government Area narrates that;

Our youths and their groups do not know what they want. That is the pathetic side of their story. This is because, the village leaders and some politicians will use them to control activities in our community and nobody will have a say in anything apart from what the leadership wants. These youth group will be promised this and that, but only few of the youth groups leaders are sometime empower by these community leaders to continue to lead other youths toward the achievement of their selfish purposes.

Narratives from majority of the respondents revealed that the youths groups and associations are used by some of the community leaders in some rural areas in Akwa Ibom State to impede development thereby promoting poverty, slavery of the rural citizenries and creating rural communal conflicts and local crises within communities. One of the respondents from Akpansung community in Esit Eket Local Government Area in his narratives stated that:

We are living here in this community because we have no other place we can call our village yet these youths will be send by community leaders to come and fight us, intimidate us, burnt down our houses and churches. We are suffering greatly, we cannot develop this place because they will come and burn down everything. They want to make us slaves in our land, they don't consider the fact that we are of one stock. All of these are because sometimes these oil companies that try to give small compensations to host communities.

One of the study participants from InuaEyet Ikot in Ibeno Local Government Area responded that:

Our youths are often used by the leaders of our community, but the painful thing that I discover is that most times these youths do not know that they are being used by these people to achieve selfish goals not the general goals of the community.

Youths and youth groups or associations participation in community activities have witness a progressive facet in recent times most especially in the rural communities as gathered from responses through indepthinterviews. The effects of this progress of youth participation in community activities has brought more of negative impacts as compare to youth community development activities in some rural communities in Akwa Ibom State as extracted from narratives among conducted interviews.

Discussion of Major Findings

Gathered data from the study participants show that marginalization, biased politics and youth groups manipulation have been long standing causes of community crises and most of the root factors of underdevelopment of most rural communities due to the rifts generated from these social problems. Study participants reported that not all the major families have been carried along by their village heads, and those who oppose anti-cultural and anti-traditional activities are often intimidated by some members of some youth groups. The resultant effects of these problems have been discovered to be group rivalries among the community stakeholders and families crises within the communities. This positioned the affected communities in the trap of underdevelopment. Study participants established marginalization, biased politics and youth groups manipulation as underlying factors behind the struggle of poverty, underdevelopment, and human slavery by some rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. Findings of the study show that selfishness on the part of community leadership has brought about the use of marginalization, biased politics and youth groups manipulation as tools toward achieving their selfish goals thereby enslaving the rural masses.

When members of the community are not carried along by their leadership, there is bound to be internal criticism which will lead to internal rift and thence community crises. Majority of the participants ($n = 221/77.5\%$) through interview narrated the danger of using marginalization as part of leadership strategies by rural community leaders. Most of which is underdevelopment of the rural areas. In their responses, the participants reported neglect, selectivity, exculsion, and rejection as measures used by some community leaders to keep some members of their rural communities from being part of profitable activities. This kept-aside practice has brought about tension within the social structure of some rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. The conflict within the social structure has impeded development, enhancing poverty and promoting slavery among rural people.

As traditional rulers as been barred from active politics in Nigeria, some of these custodians of traditional culture resort to partisan politics in their rural communities to satisfy their selfishness and achieve certain goals. Majority of the respondents ($n = 179/62.8\%$), reported that bias politics have been the interconnected force between every part, segment and activity within the social structure of some rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. It was discovered that games of lies are played between community leaders and the rural people. Deception, blackmail, accusations, libel, and other character deformative techniques are used among some rural community leaders and the rural masses as measures of overrunning each party to achieve their aimed.

One significant challenge to effective youth participation in community development programmes is what Israel, Coleman, and Ilvento, (2013) describes as not being sure of the benefits of their contributions. Majority of the study participants ($n = 212/74.4\%$) in their responses to interviews reported that rural community leaders have misled the youths toward achieving their selfish goals. It was discovered that most youths pay allegiance to their community leaders in order to be recommended for one opportunity or the other. Most of the rural youths are ignorant of the aim of their activities as directed by their community leaders, making them blinded tools in the hands of some selfish rural community leaders. From observation, cultism has been a major factor within youth groups in many rural communities in Akwa Ibom State. This make the groups to be loyal to the community leadership in order to prevent the community leadership from working against them or reporting them to the police.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study findings positioned traditional institutions in Akwa Ibom State as an institution which practices affect rural community development. Selfish interest has been a factor that drives the motives behind most actions performed by some rural community leaders. Marginalization, black politics and youth groups manipulations have been visible machineries employed by some rural community rulers to attain goals determined by selfish desire instead of the interest of the general community. The resultant effects have been the dragging of most rural community in Akwa Ibom State in the bane of underdevelopment, poverty and human slavery in an era of democratic practices.

To ensure rural community development in Africa, traditional institution should be restructure inline with democratic principles. The shift in traditional institution in Akwa Ibom State from traditional inherited rulership offices to politically attained offices calls for a legal framework for democratic principles to determine the practices and participation in rural community offices and activities. This will ensure creation of proper development channels and freedom of community participations by community members.

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